

Bridging knowledge gaps in tundra vegetation ecology in a warmer future Arctic

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Background

The Arctic is warming nearly four times faster than the rest of the planet (Rantanen et al., 2022). Arctic tundra ecosystems are responding to these rapid climate changes and subsequent environmental changes in myriad ways, with implications for wildlife habitats, permafrost, land-atmosphere interactions and regional climate, the global carbon cycle, Arctic Indigenous and local communities, and more. One of the strongest central tendencies of Arctic environmental change on land has been an increase in the aboveground biomass and productivity (“greenness”) of tundra vegetation. However, the Arctic tundra as a whole has exhibited a variety of vegetation responses – not only regional and localized increases in biomass and productivity (“greening”), but also decreases (“browning”), and stability (little or no change in vegetation). While remotely-sensed spectral indices such as the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index are useful proxies for ecosystem conditions and responses, with a period-of-record approaching 45 years, they also have significant limitations. Many knowledge gaps remain in interpreting long-term trends (and stability), while process models face considerable challenges in accurately projecting future responses as the Arctic continues to

warm. Given the high variability in ecosystem trends at the landscape scale, our knowledge base for many parts of the Arctic remains sparse. Strong interactions and feedbacks among vegetation, herbivores, decomposers, permafrost, soil hydrology, temperature regime, albedo, sea ice conditions, and disturbance further impact system dynamics.

Monitoring vegetation change across the Arctic

Long-term monitoring is crucial to understanding the patterns, magnitude, and drivers of vegetation change across the Arctic. Such monitoring requires a multi-faceted approach that incorporates both *in situ* data and remotely sensed approaches, and integrates modeling of climate, cryosphere, and ecosystem interactions with vegetation. International cooperation and dedicated funding are essential to ensure the continuity of monitoring efforts and spaceborne observation capabilities. To this end, international research initiatives such as NASA's Arctic-Boreal Vulnerability Experiment ([ABOVE](#)), and standardised monitoring networks like the International Tundra Experiment ([ITEX](#)), the Climate-ecological Observatory for Arctic Tundra ([COAT](#)), the Greenland Ecosystem Monitoring ([GEM](#)) project, the Svalbard Integrated Observation System ([SIOS](#)), and the [Arctic Report Card](#) have all been instrumental in developing a rich record of Arctic vegetation change over the past several decades. These and other research efforts have documented a persistent (but temporally and spatially heterogeneous) trend of increasing plant productivity and shrub encroachment across the Arctic (e.g. Frost et al., 2025). However, vegetation responses to ongoing warming are complex and continued effort will be required to understand and prepare for a changing Arctic. New research pushes forward efforts to understand Arctic vegetation change by:

- Monitoring understudied aspects of Arctic plant communities such as diversity in vascular plants, bryophytes and lichens (García Criado et al., 2025b).
- Highlighting ongoing 'borealization' as boreal species (beyond trees and shrubs) move into tundra ecosystems (García Criado et al., 2025a).
- Bringing genetic insights to understand tundra shrub responses to past and present climate change (Dance et al., 2025).
- Exploring shifts in plant phenology as a result of Arctic warming, acknowledging the importance of the full growing season (Karlsen et al., 2021).
- Analyzing patterns and drivers of lesser studied Arctic 'browning' events, and how these may be caused by extreme weather events, wildfire, grazing pressure and abrupt permafrost thaw (Phoenix et al., 2025; Phoenix and Treharne, 2022).
- Heading south to tackle the difficult task of monitoring vegetation change in Antarctica (Colesie et al., 2025).
- Demonstrating the power of emerging technology such as uncrewed aerial vehicles (Assmann et al., 2020; Nelson et al., 2024; Orndahl et al., 2022; Villoslada et al., 2023), time-lapse cameras (Parmentier et al., 2021), and hyperspectral imagery (Salko et al., 2024) for monitoring vegetation.

- Analyzing relationships between sea ice area variations and satellite-derived terrestrial biosphere and cryosphere parameters across the Arctic (Bartsch et al., 2025).

Continued support for innovative research like this is critical for robust monitoring of the Arctic.

Dynamic Arctic ecosystems

Acknowledging the complexity of Arctic vegetation change means acknowledging the complexity of Arctic ecosystems. These ecosystems are a complex web of interactions and feedbacks among vegetation, animals and decomposers, climate and atmosphere, disturbances, coastal processes, snow, permafrost, and soils. Increasingly, these interactions are acknowledged and considered in research about vegetation change. For example, the 'greening' of the Arctic has been primarily linked to increases in growing season temperature, but there is increasing evidence that cold season conditions (e.g. non-growing season temperature, extreme winter warming events, varying snow accumulation, frost droughts, and rain-on-snow) are equally important drivers (Dial et al., 2024; Lechler et al., 2025; Parmentier et al., 2025, 2024, 2018). Disturbances also strongly influence patterns of vegetation abundance and change across the Arctic (Foster et al., 2022; Orndahl et al., 2025). Increasing wildfires (Descals et al., 2022) and permafrost thaw (Schuur and Mack, 2018) have clear and profound impacts on Arctic vegetation. However, more diffuse disturbances such as herbivory and trampling by Arctic fauna (Barrio et al., 2025; Spiegel et al., 2023) are also critical for understanding patterns and trends of vegetation change. In some cases, these impacts are even detectable using remotely-sensed data (Paulsen et al., 2025; Siewert and Olofsson, 2021). Finally, though hidden from view, what goes on beneath the surface is critically important – this belowground ecosystem of plant roots, rhizomes, microbes, organic matter and minerals, drive patterns of plant growth and nutrient cycling that have critical impacts on Arctic ecosystems (Hewitt et al., 2019). These drivers all affect ecosystem processes at different spatial and temporal scales, thus having a diverse toolkit (e.g. *in situ* data, remote sensing, modeling, genetics, paleoecology, Traditional Ecological Knowledge) is essential to understanding dynamic Arctic ecosystems.

Linking the biosphere, cryosphere, atmosphere, and oceans

Arctic vegetation change takes place in the biosphere, which is inextricably linked to other Arctic systems: the cryosphere, atmosphere, and oceans (Bartsch et al., 2025; Parmentier et al., 2013). Thus, understanding the interactions among these spheres is critical for Arctic vegetation ecology. Earth System Models provide a way to understand and project these interactions, but have historically struggled across the Arctic biome. Few land surface models include Arctic-specific plant functional types (PFTs) and they commonly lack mosses, lichens, dynamic wetlands and thermokarst processes (Matthes et al., 2025). In general, Earth system models vastly underestimate the amount of soil carbon at high latitudes (Varney et al., 2022), which in part may be due to the challenges of modeling high latitude vegetation, including responses to

changing snow cover (Pongracz et al., 2024). New efforts seek to improve on this by including and enhancing modeling of Arctic system components such as arctic-specific plant functional types, permafrost carbon, abrupt permafrost thaw, lateral carbon transport, and snowpack structure, as well anthropogenic drivers of change (Matthes et al., 2025; Schädel et al., 2024).

Priorities for future research

- Parsing the short- versus longer-term effects of Arctic disturbances (e.g. fire, permafrost thaw, thermokarst)
- Improving understanding of ecosystem dynamics in the High Arctic and other understudied but rapidly warming regions
- Reconciling full-season net productivity and the effects of changing Arctic seasonality
- Disentangling permafrost thaw, soil nutrient, soil moisture, and surface water effects on tundra vegetation
- Examining environmental factors that promote stability and resilience in tundra ecosystems
- Cross-trophic impacts of tundra ecosystem change
- Improved representation of Arctic-specific plant functional types in land surface models
- Increased focus on changing cryptogamic cover and its impact on land-atmosphere interactions especially in the high north and Antarctica.
- Improved understanding and modeling of the effect of cold-adaptation strategies on plants
- Modeling linkages between the biosphere and other systems: atmosphere, cryosphere, oceans
- Prioritizing interdisciplinary research and co-production of knowledge with Indigenous communities

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